

VARIATION OF RELATIVE VISCOSITY WITH TEMPERATURE.
NON-AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF ELECTROLYTES AND
NON-ELECTROLYTES

BY A. C. CHATTERJI AND A. N. BOSE

The variation of relative viscosity with temperature has been studied. It has been observed that the value of $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\eta_r / \eta_0 \right)$ is negative for all the solutions studied here.

In previous communications (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 93; 1949, 26, 91) the variation of relative viscosity with temperature has been studied. In the present paper the work has been extended to a few more solutions of electrolytes and non-electrolytes in non-aqueous solvents.

Experimental method used is the same as given in the previous communications (*loc. cit.*). Results obtained are given in Table I. Concentrations are given in g. of solute per 100 g. of solvent.

TABLE I

Solute.	Conc.	30°.	35°.	40°.	45°.
	Solvent = Acetone.				
1. Benzoic acid	50.0	2.218	2.174	2.144	2.146
	60.0	2.456	2.405	2.353	2.303
2. Salicylic acid	45.5	2.093	2.046	2.015	2.020
	54.5	2.443	2.354	2.322	2.305
3. <i>o</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	67.9	3.428	3.327	3.256	3.200
	81.2	4.708	4.678	4.441	4.325
4. Phthalic acid	5.2	1.183	1.179	1.161	1.177
5. Cinnamic acid	20.4	1.617	1.605	1.581	1.592
6. <i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid	59.9	2.953	2.998	2.838	2.826
	103.5	5.514	5.312	5.203	5.058
7. Oxalic acid	11.8	1.472	1.459	1.453	1.452
	32.4	2.676	2.807	2.726	2.691

TABLE I (contd.)

Solute.	Conc.	35°.	40°.	45°.	50°.
Solvent = Methyl alcohol.					
8. KI	10.0	1.261	1.250	1.248	1.251
	20.0		1.459	1.453	1.448
9. NH ₄ Br	5.33	1.280	1.275	1.280	1.284
	12.86	1.539	1.536	1.512	1.525
10. NH ₄ NO ₃	19.60	1.680	1.662	1.652	1.656
	27.30		2.316	2.102	2.101
11. KCNS	23.70	1.964	1.942	1.910	1.907
	31.20	2.310	2.241	2.209	2.172
12. NH ₄ CNS	2.580	1.972	1.998	1.954	1.953
	3.580	2.315	2.308	2.280	2.280
40°.					
45°.					
50°.					
55°.					
Solvent = Propyl alcohol.					
13. NaI	20.01	1.605	1.594	1.575	1.552
	29.70	1.978	1.973	1.957	1.938
14. KCNS	4.32	1.132	1.270	1.321	1.222
	6.01	1.206	1.200	1.206	1.191

DISCUSSION

It may be observed that in case of all the solutions $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ is negative. So far as the acetone solutions are concerned the results are according to our expectations (Chatterji and Ram Gopal, this *Journal*, 1947, 24, 455) as both the solvent and solute are polar and the solvates formed by their combination are expected to break with rise of temperature. Solutions of electrolytes in methyl and propyl alcohols are expected to gain positive values for $\frac{\delta}{\delta t} \left(\frac{\eta_s}{\eta_0} \right)$ due to the depolymerising effect of the solute molecules, but they too have given negative values. Similar results have been obtained by Briscoe and Reinhart (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1942, 46, 387) in their study of solutions of potassium iodide in methyl alcohol. Probably the unexpected behaviour is due to the high concentration of the solutions studied.